

A semi-automated data integration workflow to enable high-throughput crop modelling

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Abstract: Crop simulation models are important tools for yield projection and analysis but are rarely used for real-time decision support due to persistent bottlenecks in data management and processing workflows to generate input datasets. We present a blueprint for a semi-automated data management workflow that enables high-throughput simulation, integrating diverse source data into a rapid, scalable pipeline. The modular workflow leverages established standards in geospatial science, agronomy, and crop modeling to assemble high-quality inputs for crop models. The blueprint outlines the technical requirements to operationalize crop models, enabling broader applications as decision-support tools.

Keywords: crop modelling, data integration, data standards, Internet-of-Things, interoperability

1 Introduction

Crop simulation models simulate plant growth and development from (meta)data inputs describing the cropping systems drivers and cultivation environment alongside ground-truth benchmarks for model validation. Applying such models for real-time decision support would require high-throughput data processing workflows, demanding efficient sourcing, standardization, and integration of these diverse data types. However, input data

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assembly is hindered by fragmented, poorly documented, and unstructured data, compounded by limited data management expertise in crop sciences [SSS22]. Widespread non-compliance with the FAIR principles for scientific data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable [Wi16]) forces researchers into ad-hoc, labor-intensive data wrangling, undermining efficiency and reproducibility. This challenge demands standardized, scalable workflows—not technological breakthroughs, but the applied integration of proven data management and science tools to streamline agronomic data processing. In the following, we propose a concept for such workflow to enable high throughput crop modelling applications, paving the way for model-assisted decision-support systems in agriculture.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data types

- **Environmental sensing data** collected with sensor and imaging technologies is increasingly used to monitor crop growth and environmental dynamics. Common sensing devices include Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensors (e.g., soil probes, weather stations) and Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for crop canopy imaging. These devices often use proprietary formats, limiting the interoperability of data streams.
- **Context and content metadata** (e.g., provenance, cultivars, management) and **manual measurements** (e.g., yield, biomass, nutrient content) are critical for model parameterization and validation, but inconsistencies in data annotation across institutions, projects, and even individual researchers limit their reusability.
- **Genotypic traits** substantially influence crop growth and development, yet relevant traits for crop models are rarely measured. They are typically estimated with optimization algorithms, risking overfitting. Model calibration is therefore dependent on expert knowledge and iterative refinement to ensure biological plausibility.
- **External data sources**, such as meteorological databases, reanalysis products, soil and climate models, are essential for filling data gaps when the description of local conditions is deficient. While these sources provide structured data, they often define their own data model and query specifications, complicating integration.

2.2 Design requirements

Core data challenges were derived from consultations with modelers and agronomists. The identified bottlenecks were used to formalize a set of foundational requirements for workflow development.

- **Modularity and extensibility:** Independent modules handle data processing and simulation, allowing updates and feature extensions without disrupting the overall workflow architecture.
- **Interoperability:** Module outputs adhere to established, domain-specific ontologies and metadata standards to ensure interoperability across modules, as well as seamless data exchange and reuse within the broader scientific community.
- **Automation and reproducibility:** Modules are combined as building blocks of custom workflows that integrate and automate data extraction, transformation, and simulation tasks. User intervention is maintained to specific inputs (e.g., data sources, calibration rules) documented in configuration files, ensuring deterministic execution without hidden or arbitrary steps.
- **Transparency and traceability:** All transformations maintain source integrity, with full provenance tracking for datasets and outputs.
- **User-accessibility:** Open-source tools (R/Python) and clear documentation support broad usability. Individual modules can be assembled in code-agnostic workflow engines or development environments, ensuring accessibility across user categories.
- **Collaborative and open data management:** FAIR-compliant outputs enable data publication in open data repositories and catalogues, fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration and continuous improvement of model inputs.

3 Results

Each data processing operation is encapsulated in an individual module (i.e., script or set of scripts). These modules are designed to be chained in sequence, where the standardized output of an upstream module serves as the input for the next. This design allows for the flexible assembly of custom workflows using the SciWIn tool [Kr25], which leverages the Common Workflow Language (CWL) to enable orchestrating code-agnostic workflows by chaining containerized tools.

3.1 Extraction processes

IoT Sensor data streams are structured and annotated using the OGC SensorThings API standard (STA), a data model that defines hierarchized entities for organizing and querying IoT data [Li21]. We use the sensorHUB platform, a software stack built upon the Fraunhofer Open Source SensorThings API Server (FROST server), an open-source implementation of the STA data model and API [GVA24]. Datastreams are transmitted to the FROST server either via LoRaWAN networks or pushed via HTTP requests through

ETL processes that handle mapping to STA endpoints. To ensure full interoperability, observed properties are annotated using established domain ontologies [Bu16].

UAV imagery. Geospatial data processing employs the OGC API Processes standard, which wraps computational tasks into executable processes accessible via a RESTful API [Pr21]. As the STA data model lacks native raster imagery support, we implemented a web service to pre-process UAV orthophotos. Spatial functions for the extraction of imagery indices are defined and created as OGC API Processes. The service computes plot-level zonal statistics for various spectral vegetation indices (e.g., NDVI, NDRE, SAVI). These statistics are then formatted as a STA-compliant JSON object and posted to the FROST server for integration with downstream processes.

Manual inputs. To address the absence of formal data structure, we developed a standardized data entry template that harmonizes the ICASA dictionary [Wh13], a widely adopted crop modeling terminology, with the BonaRes LTE data model [Ku24], which captures agronomic knowledge representations. The modular Excel template lets users select application-relevant input sections and attributes while enforcing standard compliance via dynamic data validation.

Public data sources. We simplified access to heterogeneous public data by developing wrapper functions that harmonize the structure of request payloads and response parsing across databases. Users can easily download the data using a unified set of explicit input arguments (e.g., query geocoordinates, timeframe, data source, temporal resolution).

3.2 Transformation processes

Estimation of biophysical variables from vegetation indices. Vegetation indices from sparse UAV observations are combined with weather data through a multi-stage process: NDVI measurements are first interpolated to daily time series using physiologically-informed methods constrained by wheat-specific growth patterns, then spatially and temporally aligned with weather data through geographic coordinate matching and daily resampling, while phenological variables are derived by calculating cumulative Growing Degree Days (GDD) from weather data [MW97] using crop-specific thresholds that are cross-validated against published NDVI trends to identify growth stage transitions. The combined dataset enables the estimation of Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC) using a linear mixing model where $NDVI_{soil}$ and $NDVI_{vegetation}$ parameters are estimated from literature values [GI98]. Crop-growth constraints are validated through three complementary approaches: (1) enforcing physiological bounds during interpolation (NDVI and FVC constrained to $[0, 1]$), (2) cross-referencing GDD-based phenological timing with NDVI-derived development indicators (e.g., verifying peak NDVI corresponds to flowering stage), and (3) treating observed data points as hard constraints with distance-weighted influence functions during interpolation, while uncertainty

quantification through bootstrap resampling provides confidence intervals that scale with distance from actual measurements.

Data integration and mapping. To ensure interoperability with crop modelling frameworks, extracted data are first standardized using ICASA as a canonical intermediate model. A bidirectional mapping system, governed by YAML-based rules, handles translations to and from ICASA by applying structured data operations, such as column/row transformation, term mappings, and table joins. The mapping process is executed in three steps via an orchestrator script: (1) row-wise transformations (e.g., string mapping, unit conversions, table joins), (2) format standardization (e.g., date formats, regex-based string normalization), (3) summary transformations (e.g., hourly to daily temperature). ICASA-aligned datasets are then consolidated into one single object and mapped to the target crop model schema.

Genetic parameter fitting. External software used for parameter fitting (e.g., the DSSAT framework [Ho24]) is invoked via system interface wrappers. Users set parameter bounds and iterative calibration strategies (e.g., optimization sequences), which the workflow uses to generate batch configurations before executing the calibration process programmatically.

3.3 Publication and indexing

All datasets, code, software and experimental materials involved in the workflow are registered in AgriHUB, a DCAT-compliant metadata catalog built on the open-source CKAN platform. As an instance of the Smart Rural Area Data Infrastructure [Mo20] AgriHUB promotes transparency, reusability and traceability by indexing research resources into standardized categories (e.g., online application, device/object, method, dataset...), each associated with specific metadata. The schema allows semantic linking between catalog entries, forming a knowledge graph that interconnects digital resources across the entire workflow, from field data acquisition to the simulation runs.

Results

Pilot tests confirmed the workflow's potential to enable high throughput crop modelling but also exposed a persistent bottleneck with manual data entry. Despite the use of familiar tools like Excel, data producers remain reluctant to adopt new formats, even when they enable reuse. To overcome this, future work should focus on integrating established tools (e.g., electronic field books) to streamline adoption and foster data exchange between agronomists and modelers.

Our "field-to-simulation" pipeline standardizes data using ICASA-compliant schemas, ensuring compatibility with major modeling frameworks. While validated with DSSAT

wheat models, its modular design allows rapid extension to other crops and models. This work establishes a scalable foundation for rapid crop modeling workflows, providing the technical basis for deploying crop models as decision-support tools.

References

- [Bu16] Buttigieg, P. L. et.al.: The environment ontology in 2016: bridging domains with increased scope, semantic density, and interoperation. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics* 7/1, S. 57, 2016.
- [GVA24] Gackstetter, D., Varoshi, P., Asseng, S.: sensorHUB—a novel, open-source software stack for enhanced accessibility and secure interoperability in IoT project management. *Int Arch Photogramm Remote Sens Spatial Inf Sci* XLVIII/4, S. 197–204, 2024.
- [GI98] Gutman, G.; Ignatov, A.: The derivation of the green vegetation fraction from NOAA/AVHRR data for use in numerical weather prediction models. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 19(8), 1998, pp. 1533–1543.
- [Ho24] Hoogenboom, G. et al.: Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) Version 4.8.5. DSSAT Foundation, Gainesville 2024.
- [Kr24] Krumsieck, J. et.al.: SciWin-Client, fairagro.github.io/m4.4_sciwin_client, Stand: 17.10.2025
- [Ku24] Kuehnert, T. et.al.: BonaRes LTE Data Schema, doi.org/10.20387/bonares-jrnx-r965, Stand: 22.09.2025
- [LKV24] Liang, S., Khalafbeigi, T., van der Schaaf, H.: OGC SensorThings API Part 1: Sensing Version 1.1, www.opengis.net/doc/is/sensorthings/1.1, Stand: 31.10.2025.
- [MW97] McMaster, G. S., Wilhelm, W. W.: Growing degree-days: one equation, two interpretations. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 87/4, S. 291–300, 1997.
- [Mo20] Moshrefzadeh, M. et.al.: Towards a distributed digital twin of the agricultural landscape. *Journal of Digital Landscape Architecture* 5, S. 173–186, 2020.
- [PP24] Pross, B.; Vretanos, P. A.: OGC API - Processes - Part 1: Core Version 1.0, www.opengis.net/doc/IS/ogcapi-processes-1/1.0, Stand: 31.10.2025
- [SSS22] Senft, M., Stahl, U., Svoboda, N.: Research data management in agricultural sciences in Germany: we are not yet where we want to be. *PLOS One* 17/9, PS. e0274677, 2022.
- [Wi16] Wilkinson, Mark D. et al.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3/1, S. 160018, 2016.